

**Arrogance of Ignorance: Theatre for Development (TFD) Experiment
Towards Re-orientation of Erekiti Youths**

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Abstract

The growth and development of a community depend on the people (both young and old) that inhabit the area. Their level of education, mindset, psyche and God given resources are combined together to enhance the locality. The enhancement of the community could be positive or negative depending on the people's perception of who they are as a collective entity. The Erekiti youths in Badagry Local Government Area of Lagos State are caught up at the cross roads of understanding the process of enhancing community development through their collective stand, utterance and actions. This paper, through an interventionist approach of Theatre for Development, dissected and properly analysed the communal challenge of the youth's inability to work together towards advancing social development. The paper adopted the Functionalist Theory of social development and Development Media Theory, with the combination of the homestead approach of Tfd in finding solutions to the people's problem. The findings however show that Tfd could be used as tool for raising collective consciousness towards resolving communal challenges. Knowing fully well that people, especially the youths are shaped and sharpened through social consciousness and experience. In a situation where the consciousness is silenced, Tfd then becomes the machinery for the re-awakening process.

Keywords: Arrogance, Ignorance, Pontification, Theatre for Development, Orientation.

Résumé

La croissance et le développement d'une communauté dépendent des personnes (jeunes et les personnes âgées) qui habitent la région. Leur niveau d'éducation, leur état d'esprit, leur psyché et les ressources disponibles sont tous importants pour améliorer la localité. L'amélioration de la communauté pourrait être positive ou négative selon la perception des gens de leur existence en tant qu'entité collective. Les jeunes d'Erekiti, dans le gouvernement local de Badagry, de l'État de Lagos, se trouvent actuellement au carrefour de la compréhension du processus d'amélioration du développement communautaire par leur position collective, leurs déclarations et leurs actions. Cet article, à travers l'approche interventionniste de «Theatre for Development», disséquait et analysait correctement le défi commun de l'incapacité des jeunes à travailler ensemble pour faire progresser le développement social. Le document a adopté la théorie fonctionnaliste du développement social et la théorie des médias de développement, avec la combinaison de l'approche familiale de Tfd dans la recherche de solutions au problème des personnes. Les résultats montrent cependant que le Tfd pourrait être utilisé comme un outil pour élever la conscience collective vers la résolution des défis communaux. Il faut savoir que les gens, en particulier les jeunes, sont façonnés et aiguisés à travers la conscience sociale et

l'expérience. Dans une situation où la conscience est réduite au silence, Tfd devient alors la machinerie pour le processus de réveil.

Mots-clés: Arrogance, ignorance, pontificat, théâtre pour le développement, Orientation.

Introduction

The character trait of an individual informs his psyche or vice-versa. In other words, what is meant is that the innate disposition of a being will affect or inform that person's thinking and the presentation of the 'self'. Arrogance also known as pride is a psychological and character trait in human beings that is characterized by unpleasant manifestation. It is an aspect of emotional reasoning that behoves a sense of superiority on a person or a group of people. Johnson et al (2010:23) describe it as "a set of behaviours that communicates a person's exaggerated sense of superiority, which is often accomplished by disparaging others". Etymologically, the word is rooted in Latin expression "arrongantia" meaning "pride", "presumption" and "haughtiness". In the classification of arrogance, scholars such as Ekman (2003), Mitche (2009) and Tracy and Robin (2004) have classified it into two broad categories; (1) Authentic Arrogance and (2) Hubris Arrogance. Authentic arrogance is associated with a measure of attributing success to one's effort. According to Tracey and Robin (2004:9) Authentic Arrogance "is a specific emotion that derives from an appraisal of recognition for increasing self-mastery within a given context". From this, it is clear that this form of arrogance has to do with self-pride that is always limited to time and space and tied to specific issues and events. Richard Robin (2014:5) buttresses this point when he asserts that Authentic Arrogance is not about being better than someone else, it's about being better than yourself, better than the way you used to be." The implication here is that authentic arrogance is positive in nature and it is a state of progression from bad to good or good to better. On the other hand Hubristic Arrogance is excessive pride or arrogance of self-confidence. Taking its root from the ancient Greek term "hubris", means "steps taken that shame and humiliate an individual and probably lead to regret". Lee gives it a succinct description when he claims that:

when you make yourself feel better at the expense of others- only feeling pride when others are feeling less. You only feel good about your accomplishments when comparing them to others.

Hubristic arrogance is thus negative in nature as it could degenerate into hatred, hostility, crisis and war. Hubristic arrogance has manifested in issues like racism, xenophobic attacks and ethnic and communal clashes. This paper then explores Hubristic Arrogance and its manifestations among the people (youths) of Erekiti community in Badagry. Theatre for Development was deployed as a tool of investigation and the channel of conscientising the people in order to proffer solutions to their problems.

The Concept of Theatre for Development

The attempt by theatre scholars and practitioners to use theatre as a vehicle of contributing to social development and advancement has brought about the idea of Applied Theatre which goes beyond mere entertainment to education, mobilization and conscientisation. Applied theatre, according to Adeyemi, Sola (2016:11) is an umbrella term that covers

theatre and communication practice conducted outside the mainstream theatre and communication practice, specifically for transforming or changing human behaviour for the better. Philip Taylor (1996:3) advances further that Applied theatre is characterized by its desire to influence human activity, to raise issues and have members of the audience resolving the issues". There are several branches of this form of theatre and their relative and specific functions like Forum Theatre, Community Theatre, Popular Theatre, Participatory communication, Guerilla Theatre, Theatre for Development (TfD) and Theatre for Social Development (TfSD) but for the purpose of this research work, we will restrict theatre as a tool for communication and development to the popular community theatre otherwise known as "Theatre for Development". Theatre for Development is an interventionist form of theatre practice that is used according to Epochi-Oliseh (2013:8) as a forum for "dialogue" in which all involved discuss issues that are of major interest to their individual and social development. In the field of Communication Studies, this practice is also referred to as Development Communication because the main essence of its engagement with the people is to communicate for the purpose of assessing development. For this reason, the TfD itself has been linked with Development Media Theory which relates to media structures and performance in developing societies and provides a strong theoretical basis for understanding the relationship between theatre and development. Indeed, the theatre as a medium of communication constantly mirrors and reflects the society. Beyond drawing its theme from the society, which varies from the historical to the present and the futuristic, it has been argued and rightly too that the shape, outlook and presentation of a country's theatre are direct reflections of the yearning of the people. It is these attributes that bestow on the theatre the role of a vanguard, a watchdog, the barometer of the society and a major factor in nation building (Yerima 2007).

The tools used for TfD seem to vary from location to location. The practice involves tools and processes such as:

- Conceptualizing, writing, making plays and performing;
- Art, music, song and dance;
- Analysing problems and finding their root causes;
- Children engaging with adults and other children for bringing about positive changes;
- Negotiations with those in authority.

Theatre for Development aims to offer an alternative approach and medium by which theatre can be of direct service to the marginalized urban and rural peasant masses. The TfD approach which is gaining slow ascendancy in Nigeria emphasizes collectivism and participation. It stresses community and inter-personal participation in self-realization and uses existing and familiar performance forms such as songs, dances, music, storytelling, puppetry and mime in the various communities to either validate those cultural forms or serve as an adequate instrument to bring about social change in those communities.

Going by its history, Tfd in Nigeria started from the academic activity at the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The project gained wide acceptance and many Universities and Non Governmental Organisations adopted it as a major practice for harnessing social development. There has been many other initiatives in the past like plays that focused on government programmes such as the national food production initiative dubbed Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) and the Green Revolution programme of the Federal Government, although underscoring the role of theatre in identifying and analysing societal problems and in mobilizing target audiences particularly the grass root towards addressing developmental issues.

Theatre for Development has thus become a Sustainable Form of Community Growth that should be infused into every process of developmental process in any given community. This is because its first mission is to investigate the problems of the given community through raking, (raking involves the visit to the host community in order to gather vital information that could help the Tfd team in preparing themselves for their host. It also involves carrying the host communities a long, preparing and paying the community leader a visit. A sustainable development must be that which directly involves the consciousness of the host community, the acceptance by the host community, and the involvement of the host community.

Theoretical Framework

The theories adopted for this research, as mentioned earlier are Functionalist Theory and Development Media Theory. Functionalist Theory is a theory in sociology whose main thrust according to Ritzer (1996:235) is that all societies have basic need-functional requirement which must be met if the society is to survive. Functionalists are therefore concerned with the contribution which various parts of the society, including the youths make towards fulfilling the social need. The aim of this theory is to bring about social order to the collective participation of everyone involved. According to Judith Wayne (2013:356):

When Functionalists study "society", therefore, they look initially at institutional arrangements and relationships, since these are seen as the basic building-blocks of any society. The way in which institutions relate to one another determines the structure and basic character of any society.

This theory is relevant to Tfd because it emphasizes collective responsibility to social development, which is the major reason for the social engagement of Tfd practice. The Development Media Theory encompasses what Folarin (1998:45) describes as a great variety of socio-cultural, economic and political condition which borders on the effective use of the media for development purpose. Specifically, the theory considers the role of the media in society as essential target at stimulating and sustaining societal development in such areas as cultural, social economic, political and technological development. The theory also advocates a situation where the media (theatre as one) should accept and help in carrying out the special development tasks of national integration, socioeconomic modernization, promotion of literacy and cultural creativity (Folarin 1998). The theory provides yet another basis for understanding the relationship of theatre and development. Leovinger's position is that the media 'mirrors the society' and that while the media

themselves reflects society as organized group, individual audience members project their own individual reflections into images presented. This is where the saying among theatre scholars that 'theatre is a creator's mirror of the whole universe' and the popular dictum 'the world is a stage where everyone plays his or her own part and leaves' find justification.

Erekiti/Likithi Theatre for Development Workshop

Theatre for Development (TfD) is a core course in the Department of Theatre Arts and Music, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos, Nigeria. The course is designed to train the students on the application of theatre pedagogy and empowerment strategies for social development. As a practice oriented course, the students, alongside their lecturer, liaison persons, resource persons, facilitators are expected to research into the development needs of a community, collate the data obtained in the field and finally turn same into a drama sketch to educate the community.

The Erekiti/Likithi TfD workshop was organised by the Department for the 300 level full time students with their campus at Ojo, Lagos, Nigeria and the 400 level part time students of the same Department that has its campus at Festac, Nigeria. The two levels (300 and 400) were combined to form the contingents for 2015 TfD workshop under our discussion.

Historical Origin of Erekiti/Likithi Community

Erekiti community is in Badagry Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. The first two (2) persons that were believed to be the founders of this community migrated from the Republic of Benin (Dahomeh then) were Late Pa. Gbowu from Atake in Port-Novo in the year 1723 and Late Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe. They both ran for their dear lives during the Dahomeh war. Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe settled at Akitiji. They came through Madejonu and passed through Yewa River. Pa. Gbowu and Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe met on their journey to Nigeria. Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe and Pa. Gbowu were close friends in Dahomeh and as God would have it, both of them met as they were logging all round before getting to their destination. They consulted the Oracle (Ifa) and the Oracle directed them to cross the river and anywhere they see a hill, that place will be their destination, where they will dwell forever. Pa. Hungba Hunvoepe hailed from "Vetho Thesa Gbeogbotho" in the Republic of Benin and he named his settlement "Gbegbotho" because he was a professional hunter and farmer. Pa. Gbowu was a professional fisherman and farmer; he named his own settlement "Likiti-Topa" because the place was Akitiji – meaning hill. Both of them were living without any hindrance. Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe always went for his hunting exercises. One day as he was hunting he met a man called "Pa. Oteni" who was from "Gese, Ado-Odo" and had a brief conversation with him. During their discussion Oteni made it known to Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe that he came all along from "Gese, Ado-Odo" to set fishing traps (Aja in Egun Language) to catch fishes in this swampy area. Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe and Pa. Oteni became friends through this medium and so Pa. Hugna allowed Pa. Oteni to his residence in Gbegotho where he spent seven days before he turned to his house in Ado-Odo.

During Pa. Oteni's seven days visit in Pa. Hunga's house, Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe took him to Pa. Gbowu's abode, they narrated how they met. Meanwhile Pa. Hunga could not announce Pa. Oteni's name properly, instead he called him by his special handiwork "Ajano",

meaning “Fish trap maker”. In the process both of them welcomed him and agreed to give Pa. Oteni a portion of land to live with his family and perform his duty. The place given to him was called “Ajano Likiti”. After they had settled Pa. Oteni with the piece of land and all of them living in peace, each time they met (Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe and Pa. Gbowu), they would ask “did you see Ajano today”. That is where the name of the place “Erekiti Jaron” was derived from till today. The war in Dahomeh was so much that people had to fee for their dear lives. As people were trooping out of Dahomeh in Republic of Benin, some many of them found their way to Likiti-topa which had Pa. Hunga Hunvoepe and Pa. Gbowu as the first settlers and landowners.

The following were the families that came for refuge at Likiti-Topa:

1. Wheke Family
2. Vethokoh Family
3. Tori-Torikoh Family
4. Gblegbonmeh Family
5. Togo Family
6. Aviakanmeh Family

Erekiti Tfd workshop

The journey to the workshop community – Erekiti started on the 27th of February, 2015 from the Department of Theatre Arts and Music where participants, resource persons and the workshop facilitator loaded their luggage into the buses provided. Arriving at the workshop community and as custom demands, the group headed straight to the palace of Baale Agitho, Chief Phillips S. Hunpe. The Baale received us normally with the assurance that we will have a good relationship with the community because their custom has no barrier in whatever form against visitors “especially students who are doing research for their betterment...”

The Baale took us to the accommodation he secured for the workshop – a three bungalow (Hut) newly built together and we immediately set to work. All the boys had to offload the vehicles especially the bus that contained buckets, mattresses, domestic cooking utensils, food stuffs in their bags and the numerous bags of the participants. The girls were saddled with the responsibilities of sweeping, washing and mopping of the buildings allocated to us. The first day was used for keeping/putting things properly where they belong. Temporary sheds were constructed for rehearsals and plenary. Temporary toilets and bathrooms were constructed behind the buildings, to help facilitate our job. Committees and sub-committees were announced. For example, committee in charge of cooking with its roaster of each participant taking turn to cook, Accommodation Committee, responsible for allocation of mattresses and bed spaces, Transport Disciplinary Committee comprising all resource persons headed by a camp commandant and most importantly, Physical Health Need Assessment Committee “PHENA”. This committee was in charge of health care of everybody on board. Therefore, any case of pain, injuries or domestic accidents was taken care of by the PHENA group.

The facilitator explained explicitly the dos and don'ts of the workshop to all and before the end of the day, this writer (group leader of the workshop) in the company of some of the resource persons (who speak and understand Egun language – the language of the community visited the four Baales that control Erekiti community.

In other words, as geographically small as Erekiti is, it is governed by four Baales with each Baale carving a sort of empire for himself with his loyalists. They are: Chief Waheed A. Ashade (Baale Erekiti), Chief Abila Philips S. Hunga (Baale Agitho, Likiti), Chief Abila Osedowen Azonnagbo (Baale Oglo, Likiti), Chief Gbento (Baale Ethekekanmeh, Likiti). As custom and tradition demand, each Baale was given a bottle of Schnapps as a token of good will. The Baales welcomed us after hearing from the group leader and promised to make our story memorable. This opportunity was used by the group leader to officially invite the Baales and their communities and loyalists to the opening ceremony the following day.

Arriving back at the camp, an exclusive plenary session was held involving all resource persons and the facilitator to discuss the docility of the youths, the looming apathy and chaos, anti-development traits that hang in the community. After a deep discussion on this issue, it was agreed that we engage the four Baales in a meeting after the opening ceremony holding the next day. The meeting with the Baales opened up a can of worms. The story is that, the youths of Erekiti were not lazy because most of them had one or two things doing such as: riding an Okada (motorcycle) that ferries people and loads to the community boundaries where they can access vehicles. Some took to farming though, not that profitable but it kept body and soul together. Some were into fishing. Sadly, the grazing areas became a thing of the past for the youths. The present situation is that the road is in a deplorable state, making it impossible to carry people on Okada (commercial motorcycle). The biting unemployment has not helped issues, youths of Erekiti have no place to turn to but sit in clusters each time the day breaks, withdrawn into individual's thought. With these shocking revelations, we showed our appreciation to the Baales for informing us of this big problem early enough and promised that the Tfd theme will not depart from this community until the myth created by the youths around themselves is undone through our conscious and cautious pontification.

The problem of Erekiti youths was presented at a larger plenary, serious discussion on it was made and through analysis which brought the group to an agreement that all groups should have as their member at least one Egun speaking participant and resource person that will concentrate on the youths by explaining to them our mission and vision bearing in mind that the theme of the workshop is "Leadership in a democratic dispensation". This project could not be actualized without the co-operation and participation of the youths. The various groups were given the names of the clans that constitute Erekiti that they will cover. These clans are: Gberegbonme, Gbegotho, Vethoko, Togo, Topa, Wheke, Toriko, Whethethon, Aviakanme, Jaron. This is where the Yoruba settled, Goro, Agitho. While the deities that inhabit Erekiti which everybody must reverence and recognized are the following: Atinga,

Treno, Gamla. The acolytes of this deity drinks blood when they are in trance, Aragbo – the deity is for the Ogbanjes, Othan – Snake deity, Ofa-Ifa in Yoruba.

Each time the groups went into the community for data collection, plenary sessions were held to further analyse the data from the field. This did not only give us the opportunity to tie up and tidy areas that needed attention but gave us the chance to examine and re-examine, validate facts and ground truth areas of confusions. As the groups came back from data collection and the facts from the community were revealed, all the groups took turn to tell us their experience using the participatory methodology that was agreed upon that the youths are beginning to pick interest in our work. About four out of the groups, especially the group led by Kotin (one of the resource persons and also a son of the soil) revealed that majority of the youths have shown their readiness to join the Tfd contingent as soon as we get to the stage of scenario building. This did not only gladden us, it boosted our morale and we saw the writing on the way of good success. We did not waste time in agreeing that the play that was going to emerge from this joint brainstorming of the Tfd participants and the youths of Erekiti will be called “AGBAJOWO” (Togetherness). Itemizing and isolating issues from the few days of data collection are the following points that constitute the problems of the community: poor infrastructure, unavailability of industry, supremacy conflict, unavailability of secondary school, no stable electricity supply, unavailability of Health Care Unit, racism, lack of market, unemployment, low education/parental educational ignorance, unavailability of Health care/maternity home, laziness, interrupted power supply, lack of commerce, dependent on government, division of power, lack of confidence/human defense, lack of education, youth sub-legislation, religious dogmatism, lack of unity, lack of good roads, disunity amongst the Baales, disunity amongst the youths, different customs and beliefs, high level of illiteracy, corruption, lack of recreation centre, religion and occupation.

At the level of scenario building for the Tfd performance, interested community members volunteered to be involved. This shows the evidence of the participatory nature of Tfd. The participants taught them a number songs and dance steps while they also did the same. They even brought their drums. This did not only add glamour to the whole project but it set the camp agog. The synopsis that was jointly arrived at is as follows: the play revolves around an elderly woman “Mama Agba” who doubles as a story teller. She tells the children of the community different tales. Lest we forget, children also played very important roles in the Erekiti Tfd workshop through their group dance, group song rendition that touched the hearts of all during the performance. So, the play opens with children gathering as usual doing the moon light play and games obviously waiting for “Mama Agba” to arrive. Mama Agba arrives and tells them a story from “Ilu Oke”. “Ilu Oke” is situated around the hill side of the river, the people of this community are loving people, they cherish and accommodate visitors. Their occupation is majorly fishing and farming because they have a ready market for their produce. These people are also religiously alert and have lived in peace, harmony and love until the day the white men came into their government. The arrival of the white men eroded all the values of the community because almost everybody in the community went for the goodies that the white men promised them but was not fulfilled. Because of the inability of the white men to fulfill their promises, the community was thrown into chaos,

disunity, apathy just to mention a few. One of the major problems is the disenchantment and absolute withdrawal of the youths in whatever happens in Erekiti community.

The Performance

In the evening of the tenth day of our story, all the Baales, their chiefs, their elders, the council members and their various communities with some few representatives from Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos Nigeria, that sponsored the workshop were all gathered to see the miracle that will be performed by the Tfd contingent in the face of this disunity and pluralisation. As the play began and the dances were presented alongside with the children dances, Erekiti audiences were taken by surprise to see some of their children addressing them in their songs. The key message in the children song is “You people forget we are the leaders of tomorrow so we will not forgive you if you don’t put things right and forget your differences”. The biggest scenario was the scene that focused on the arrogance of the youths over the social degeneration of things in the community. The scene was a reflection of the social reality of the youths’ ways of life in the community. The youths made it clear to everybody that the days of arrogance had become a thing of the past, the era of arrogance was also gone with this performance. The message of the youth in the play to all and sundry is – we do not have any other home so, let us work together as one to build Erekiti so that the future of everybody can be guaranteed.

Post-Performance Discussion

The drama presented provoked serious discussion when it ended as the narrator engaged the community members and asked questions about their feelings about the play. The three traditional chiefs present were able to comment that the performance showcased the actual happenings in the community and they had learnt their lessons from it, hence, the community would come together and source for solutions to their collective challenges. The community youth president also commented that the play mirrored the community’s collective existence and the youths’ insensitivity to their peculiar challenges. The community was not united and the cankerworm of disunity had eaten deep into the fabric of leadership. He however used the opportunity to appeal to the traditional leaders and the entire community to let them work together and create new avenues for moving the community forward in the area of development. At the end, the Tfd contingent visited the traditional rulers one after the other to further conscientise them on the need to call for a “Town Hall Discussion” where all issues affecting them will be discussed and probable solutions should be collectively decided.

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